

**Improving Performance of Low-Rank Matrix Completion
Algorithms Through Debiasing of Sampling Patterns**

by

Danil Platonov

A THESIS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT
OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF

BACHELOR OF SCIENCE

in

THE FACULTY OF SCIENCE

(Combined Honours Physics and Mathematics)

The University of British Columbia

(Vancouver)

April 2020

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Abstract

A solution to low-rank matrix completion is a matrix M of rank r that is much smaller than the dimensions of M and that has to be recovered from a particular sampling of M under the sampling pattern Ω , possibly with noise. This problem has wide applications, such as sensor localization, collaborative filtering and quantum state tomography.

This is a well-studied problem in the case of uniform sampling patterns, but little work is done for the non-uniform regime. In this paper we explore possible ways to accelerate state-of-the-art matrix completion algorithms using recent work on debasing simple single-step completion algorithms.

Table of Contents

Abstract	ii
Table of Contents	iii
List of Tables	v
List of Figures	vi
Acknowledgments	x
1 Motivation	1
2 Introduction	4
2.1 Probabilistic sampling patterns	7
3 Method	9
4 Algorithms	12
4.1 Single-step singular valued decomposition low-rank projection . .	12
4.2 Multi-step singular valued decomposition low-rank projection . .	14
4.2.1 Numerical experiments	16
4.3 Alternating least squares	22
4.3.1 Numerical experiments	29
4.4 Comparison of debiased SVD and debiased Fast ALS algorithms .	35
5 Conclusion and Future Work	39

5.1 Future Work	40
Bibliography	42
A Modified softImpute package code	45

List of Tables

Table 4.1	Left: sampling densities. Right: Convergence distances. For this experiment a 150×150 matrix was split into 4 equal parts by putting one separator horizontally, and one vertically.	15
Table 4.2	SVD & ALS: Fitting parameters and residuals statistics. m is the linear coefficient of proportionality, b is a constant bias, above is the maximum of residuals, below is the minimum of residuals, std is standard deviation of residuals.	20
Table 4.3	ALS-movielens: Final convergence values, and the base offset. Base offset is there to make the log version of the plot nicer. debiased (scalar) is the same as debiased, but a median of rank-1 approximation of sampling matrix is taken instead of the actual rank-1 approximation	32
Table 4.4	Synthetic data set: Convergence distance after 100 steps for SVD, ALS, and their debiased versions. Three samples are taken. $n=200$, $r=1$, sampling pattern=1-1-1-1, $p00=0.2$, $p01=0.3$, $p10=0.1$, $p11=0.4$	36

List of Figures

Figure 1.1	Left: a linear one dimensional object. Right: a non-linear one dimensional object. Both objects are one dimensional, but only the first one would work nicely with matrix completion	3
Figure 2.1	General idea of matrix completion: a low-rank matrix (that is, a matrix that is factorizable into two factors that are much smaller than its own size) is recovered from a subset of its entries that is much smaller than its size (the sampling pattern is sparse).	5
Figure 2.2	Left: $\text{rank}(X) = 1$ unit sphere. It should be understood that $\text{rank}(X)$ is scale-invariant: it won't change if X is multiplied by a non-zero number, so the lines are not bounded. Right: its convex relaxation.	6
Figure 2.3	Left: $\text{rank}(X) = 2$ sphere. Again, it should be understood that $\text{rank}(X)$ is scale-invariant: it won't change if X is multiplied by a non-zero number, so the planes are not bounded. Right: its convex relaxation. Not that $\text{rank}(X) = 2$ sphere is not a simple scaling of $\text{rank}(X) = 1$ sphere. This hints that perhaps nuclear norm isn't the best proxy for the rank function (in a sense that a different norm might perform better, for example max-norm). Also note that the generating rectangles in the picture are somewhat arbitrary. Any 2d-shape that lies in the orthogonal planes would work.	6

Figure 3.1	Different types of sampling patterns used in this thesis.	10
Figure 3.2	Different types of sampling patterns used in this thesis. Bipar- tite graph representation.	11
Figure 4.1	Top: convergence distance vs iteration. Bottom: sampling pat- tern; white means sampled, black means not sampled. Con- vergence distance was computed for the whole matrix, not just the region with non-zero sampling density, hence the distance doesn't go to zero.	15
Figure 4.2	SVD: Convergence distance vs debiaser value for several sam- ples of sampling pattern of uniform probability. Notice that the optimum is not the same for a fixed p . Also notice that the left branch of each graph has much larger slope than the right branch.	17
Figure 4.3	SVD: If more iterations are taken, minimum value does not shift.	18
Figure 4.4	SVD: As algorithm converges more and more, it hits a plateau. I think it might be there due to the svd algorithm: it stops when change is too small. Hence, in further experiments, we better make sure we don't hit this region: algorithm needs to termi- nate before we reach that zone.	19
Figure 4.5	SVD: Debiaser minimums vs number of iterations for several samples of sampling patterns.	20
Figure 4.6	SVD: Correlation of debiaser with first two singular values of sampling pattern, and means of rank-1 and rank-2 approxima- tions of the sampling pattern. $n = 100$, $r = 1$, $p = 0.3$, number of samples = 1000	21
Figure 4.7	SVD: Correlation of debiaser with deviation of row and col- umn means from the general mean. $n = 100$, $r = 1$, $p = 0.3$, number of samples = 1000	22
Figure 4.8	SVD: Optimal debiaser as a function of sampling density. . .	23
Figure 4.9	ALS: Convergence distance vs debiaser value for several sam- ples of sampling pattern of uniform probability. Using warm start, curves become much smoother. Still can see the plateau caused by numerical errors, so need to be careful to avoid it. . .	30

Figure 4.10	ALS: Optimal debiaser vs number of iterations.	31
Figure 4.11	ALS: Optimal debiaser as a function of sampling density. . . .	32
Figure 4.12	ALS: Convergence distance vs debiaser value for several sam- ples of sampling pattern of uniform probability. Like in the SVD case, optimum is not the same for a fixed p . Also notice that the left branch of each graph has much larger slope than the right branch. We thus can use the maximum of these as a debiaser value for a fixed p . On the other hand, we can try other things too. Like use first two singular values of sampling pattern instead of sampling density. A difference from SVD case is that things are very noisy: this is due to the random initial guess. If we use SVD-based warm start, then the noise disappears.	33
Figure 4.13	Debiased (matrix&scalar debiaser) vs non-debiased ALS, per- formed on the movielens dataset, with maxrank set to 100, and lambda to 50.	34
Figure 4.14	Histogram of values of rank-1 approximation of sampling pat- tern for the MovieLens dataset.	35
Figure 4.15	SVD, ALS + debias: sample 1	36
Figure 4.16	SVD, ALS + debias: sample 2	37
Figure 4.17	SVD, ALS + debias: sample 3	38

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank my supervisor Prof. Yaniv Plan for his direction and guidance, for conveying a knowledge and interest in the topic to me, and for his time spent on the project. Besides that, I would like to thank Prof. Ozgur Yilmaz for agreeing to be a second reader for the thesis project, and Prof. Rob Kiefl for teaching the honours thesis course.

I would also like to thank Elizabeth Xiao for assistance with \LaTeX . In addition, I would like to thank my friend who preferred to stay anonymous for letting me use their server to run the simulations. Furthermore, I am thankful to my parents for feeding me and providing a place to live at while writing a thesis.

I am thankful to my grandmother for cooking such delicious meals every day.

Chapter 1

Motivation

Matrix completion is used in a lot of areas. It is a part of a much larger framework of compressed sensing which deals with recovering signals that are sparse in some domain, but not in the domain in which they are measured.

For example, take an image taken by a camera. Such images are never a collection of random pixels – they are correlated with each other. It is obvious if one considers the fact that picture is projection of real 3d world on some flat surface. In the scales on which we live, reality is not made out of random, uncorrelated, particles. It is made out of objects which are a bunch of particles that are correlated with each other in some way.

Such structure is seen not in just our physical world, but also in natural languages, activity of neural networks [20], citation counts in scientific literature [17], earthquake magnitudes, wealth, number of emails and phone calls received, and many others [14]. This pattern is related to the Zipf's law (frequency of data is governed by a power law probability distribution) and Pareto principle (also known as 80/20 rule; for example, "20% of people are holding 80% of wealth", "20% of developers do 80% of work", "80% of users use only 20% of functionality", "80% of content is written in 20% of this thesis"; the ratio 20/80 doesn't have to be exact, of course).

Pareto principle is very illustrative of a general framework used in compressed sensing. For instance, saying that "20% of people are holding 80% of wealth" doesn't mean that those 20% are the most interesting people. It just means, that

they are most interesting for the wealth metric. In this case, wealth is a basis, and 20% is the dimension of the subspace that the wealthiest people occupy. Choosing which basis is the right one depends on the problem and can be very hard in some cases.

Compressed sensing deals with a much more general set of problems. For example, recovering a modulated radio wave from a noisy environment is an example of application of compressed sensing as it involves taking modes with only certain frequencies out of the stream of data, and discarding the others. In this case, the signal is sparse in the Fourier domain – that is, only a few Fourier components are required to recover it.

An interesting problem is encoding images as vectors, so that similar images have similar vectors (with respect to some similarity function like Euclidean distance, angle, or inner product). This is, for example, how one can make a service similar to Google image search. Other things can also be encoded as vectors – for example, words can be encoded into vectors in such a way so that words with similar meanings have similar vectors. Furthermore, algebraic properties can be defined on top of them, so that one can find the closest word to the sum of two other words [13] (classical example: “king” - “men” + “woman” = “queen”).

A very common modern application of matrix completion is collaborative filtering [11] – a website with some commodities that are consumed by users can use their browsing history to infer their opinion on products that are provided (or by asking for direct feedback, for example, by making them rate movies), and then apply matrix completion on this data to predict other products in which users might be interested in, thus raising amount of their sales.

A generalization of matrix completion, that uses any projections, rather than just the ones possible with the sampling set formulation (see below), can be used in quantum state tomography to recover density matrices [5].

The biggest problem with high-dimensional spaces is there is too much space – the volume of unit hypercube grows exponentially. Thus, it is often the practice in machine learning and data science to first reduce the dimensionality of the problem, for example, by doing PCA (Principle Component Analysis), which is implemented by SVD (Singular Value Decomposition). But if the dimensionality of the problem will be reduced anyway, why not just collect data in low dimen-

Figure 1.1: Left: a linear one dimensional object. Right: a non-linear one dimensional object. Both objects are one dimensional, but only the first one would work nicely with matrix completion

sions to begin with? This is where matrix completion comes to the aid as it allows recovering the low-rank data from sparse number of samples.

Another example of such problem is spectral graph drawings – we construct a matrix that contains graph-theoretical distances between the vertices of the graph, and then take the 2-dimensional projection of this matrix to use as a coordinates of points in a plane to get a nicely-looking drawing of a graph [4]. Again, using matrix completion, we don't actually need to compute all the distances, thus simplifying the problem significantly.

Also note that matrix completion is inherently a framework for recovering linear objects, see Figure 1.1. Even though the second object is one dimensional, if it wiggles in random directions in high dimensional space, it would not be possible to recover it using matrix completion. Some preprocessing steps would be required, and/or the algorithms would have to be modified in certain ways [22].

Chapter 2

Introduction

Let \hat{M} be $n \times m$ matrix of rank r . It is usually assumed that r is much smaller than the minimum of n and m (at least an order of magnitude smaller), hence it is low-rank matrix completion. We measure its entries, and record the information about what was seen in the sampling set $\Omega = \{(i, j) : (i, j) \text{ measured}\}$. In practice, we often are not able to measure everything, and this set is very sparse.

There are two approaches to studying matrix completion, based on the sampling set structure: microscopic, where we account for the exact pattern, and macroscopic, where we instead study overall statistical structure of the sampling set. In both cases, convergence guarantees are often expressed either from exact structure or the statistical properties (in the second case, convergence guarantees are probabilistic, i.e. "algorithm converges with probability p "). For convenience, we denote X_Ω to be the zero-padded version of X :

$$(X_\Omega)_{i,j} = \begin{cases} X_{i,j} & (i, j) \in \Omega \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Let's also define X_{Ω^\perp} :

$$(X_{\Omega^\perp})_{i,j} = \begin{cases} X_{i,j} & (i, j) \notin \Omega \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Sometimes we will refer to the Ω matrix, and by that we mean a binary matrix

Figure 2.1: General idea of matrix completion: a low-rank matrix (that is, a matrix that is factorizable into two factors that are much smaller than its own size) is recovered from a subset of its entries that is much smaller than its size (the sampling pattern is sparse).

whose (i,j) th entry is 1 if (i,j) is in Ω , and 0 otherwise.

We can now formally define matrix completion problem as an optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\hat{M}}{\text{minimize}} && \frac{1}{2} \|(\hat{M} - M)_{\Omega}\|_{Frob}^2 \\ & \text{subject to} && \text{rank}(\hat{M}) = r \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

Above works if rank is known. If rank is unknown, we can use:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\hat{M}}{\text{minimize}} && \text{rank}(\hat{M}) \\ & \text{subject to} && (\hat{M} - M)_{\Omega} = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

Problem (2.2) is NP-hard because rank function is integer-valued and the rank- r unit ball (i.e. set of points X so that $\text{rank}(X) \leq r$) is very spiky (see Figure 2.2 and Figure 2.3). Hence, a common way to solve this problem in practice is to conduct a convex relaxation: we replace $\text{rank}(X)$ by nuclear norm, $\|X\|_* = \{\text{sum of singular values of } X\}$. Motivation for this procedure is that this is the tightest convex cover of the spiky rank function. In turn, convexity makes this problem much easier to study and work with. In fact, it was shown that, using nuclear norm as a proxy for rank allows exact recovery of a huge class of matrices, with strong statistical guarantees [2]. Research on this subject involves semidefi-

Figure 2.2: Left: $\text{rank}(X) = 1$ unit sphere. It should be understood that $\text{rank}(X)$ is scale-invariant: it won't change if X is multiplied by a non-zero number, so the lines are not bounded. Right: its convex relaxation.

Figure 2.3: Left: $\text{rank}(X) = 2$ sphere. Again, it should be understood that $\text{rank}(X)$ is scale-invariant: it won't change if X is multiplied by a non-zero number, so the planes are not bounded. Right: its convex relaxation. Not that $\text{rank}(X) = 2$ sphere is not a simple scaling of $\text{rank}(X) = 1$ sphere. This hints that perhaps nuclear norm isn't the best proxy for the rank function (in a sense that a different norm might perform better, for example max-norm). Also note that the generating rectangles in the picture are somewhat arbitrary. Any 2d-shape that lies in the orthogonal planes would work.

nite programming, which is well understood theoretically, but not very scalable in practice for the problem of matrix completion.

On the other hand, different class of solvers, based on (2.1) formulation, are much faster in general. This problem does assume that the rank of the matrix is known, but there are ways to get rid of this requirement, for example, by using thresholding (periodically removing larger singular values when they become too small). Two such solvers are iterative SVD-feasible set projections and alternating least squares [9]. The first one is convex and has unique solution, while the second one has more than one minimum, and hence, does not have a unique solution in general. Fortunately, it can be made to have a single solution under some conditions. The reason why one would bother with the ALS over SVD algorithm is that the first one seems to be faster [9], and it is also readily parallelizable (and hence, scalable). On the other hand, there are parallel SVD algorithms too [15] [1], so it might make sense to use SVD instead, because it's somewhat less capricious than ALS.

Another interesting direction of research is max norm regularizers. They are interesting because they provide a better proxy for the rank function than the nuclear norm [21]. Furthermore, there have been some work on fast practical implementations [12]. Max-norm is defined as:

$$\|X\|_{max} = \inf\{\|U\|_{2,\infty}\|V\|_{2,\infty} : X = UV^T\}$$

where $\|\cdot\|_{2,\infty}$ denotes the maximum ℓ_2 row norm of a matrix:

$$\|A\|_{2,\infty} = \max_j\{(\sum_k A_{j,k}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}\}$$

This norm directly encodes minimization of $\|U\|_{2,\infty}$ and $\|V\|_{2,\infty}$, which are sometimes added separately as regularizers, for example, to the nuclear norm.

2.1 Probabilistic sampling patterns

In the setting of probabilistic sampling patterns, we treat Ω as a random set $\Omega = \{(i, j) | (i, j) \text{ with probability } p_{i,j}\}$, and X_Ω becomes a random variable:

$$(X_{\Omega})_{i,j} = \begin{cases} X_{i,j} & \text{with probability } p_{i,j} \\ 0 & \text{with probability } 1 - p_{i,j} \end{cases}$$

We can then compute the expectation value of the random variable X_{Ω} :

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{\Omega})_{i,j} = X_{i,j}p_{i,j} + 0(1 - p_{i,j}) = X_{i,j}p_{i,j}$$

In the case of uniform sampling patterns, we fix the probability to be the same for all indices:

$$\mathbb{E}X_{\Omega} = Xp$$

It was noted before [19] that the fact that expected value of sampled matrix is in fact proportional to the sampling probability causes matrix completion algorithms to be biased. I.e. during each iteration step, they give an answer, that is, on the average, away from the solution by a constant bias (for fixed iteration step; as more iterations are taken, bias decreases). This in turn means that convergence of those algorithms could be improved by debiasing them.

Chapter 3

Method

Throughout this paper we use a number of tools and approaches which will be described in this section in detail.

Most of simulations are done in R language using RStudio [16] (R version 3.6.2 (2019-12-12)). To set up the environment, and simplify reproducibility of results on different systems, we used R Docker image 3.6.2. We used LRSim function from denoiseR package to generate low rank matrices [10]. It works by sampling a $n \times m$ matrix from a standard multivariate normal distribution, and then applying singular value decomposition, and only keeping r singular values. After that the matrix is scaled so that the variance of each column is 1. Thus, this was only used for small matrices. We used igraph package [3] along with graphlayouts [18] extension to draw graphs of sampling patterns with adjacency matrix layout.

For the ease of comparison with previous work, we have used softImpute package [8] that implements the non-debiased version of the main algorithms studied, it is discussed in detail in [9]. We modify the code in this package so that it now supports debiased version of algorithms. In addition to that, we modify it in such a way so that it's easier to analyze the behaviour of algorithm (for example, we implemented the feature to compute the distance to the original, fully-measured matrix, at each iteration of the algorithm).

Throughout this thesis, we use a number of different types of sampling patterns: uniform, 1-1, 3-1, 1-1-1-1. The first one is just a usual uniform sampling pattern. For the second one, we split the sampling matrix into two equal parts by

Figure 3.1: Different types of sampling patterns used in this thesis.

a horizontal cut, each part having different uniform sampling density. For 3-1, we do the same thing, but instead of splitting into equal parts, we split into $3/4$ and $1/4$ parts, which have the ratio of 3-1, hence the name. For the last one, 1-1-1-1, we first split the sampling matrix into two equal parts by a horizontal cut, and then by a vertical cut. We then assign different probability to each partition. See Figure 3.1.

One can also think of the sampling pattern as an incidence matrix for a bipartite graph. We visualize those in Figure 3.2 using spectral graph layout which computes positions of vertices using first two singular vectors of the adjacency matrix. We can see that there are two separate clusters of the same colour in the 1-1 and 3-1 plots, with the one of the clusters in 3-1 plot smaller than in 1-1 plot. This reflects different sampling density, and only horizontal splitting of the sampling matrix. In the 1-1-1-1 plot we see two clusters of each colour. This reflects both horizontal and vertical splitting. In uniform case, there are only one cluster of each colour, reflecting uniform sampling density.

Figure 3.2: Different types of sampling patterns used in this thesis. Bipartite graph representation.

Finally, to do optimizations, we used standard R tools – *optimize* and *optim* commands.

Chapter 4

Algorithms

In this chapter we are first going to study matrix completion algorithms that use SVD at their core. We will first look at a simple single-step algorithm, and then at its iterative generalization. Debiasing will be applied to both of them. After that we will look at the alternating least squares algorithms. We will discuss the differences between the classical ALS and Fast ALS, and debias the later one.

4.1 Single-step singular valued decomposition low-rank projection

Consider a simple one-step algorithm for matrix completion (it was studied in [19]):

$$\hat{X} = \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(X_\Omega)$$

Here, $\text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}$ is a function that projects its input to the closest rank- r subspace. It can be implemented using singular value decomposition by computing SVD of X_Ω and only keeping first r singular values. Formally:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(X_\Omega) = \underset{\hat{M}}{\text{argmin}} \quad & \frac{1}{2} \|\hat{M} - M_\Omega\|_{Frob}^2 \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \text{rank}(\hat{M}) = r \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

One can imagine writing down the Taylor expansion of the projection operator:

$$\hat{X} = \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(X_\Omega) = A_0 + A_1 X_\Omega + A_2 (X_\Omega)^2 + \dots$$

Here, A_0 is an $n \times m$ tensor, A_1 – $n \times m \times n \times m$ tensor, and so on. Multiplication is to be understood in a way that, for example, each entry of $A_1 X_\Omega$ is a linear combination of entries of X_Ω , each entry of $A_2 (X_\Omega)^2$ is a quadratic combination of entries of X_Ω , and so on.

We can simplify this expression by noting that $A_0 = 0$, because $\text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(0) = 0$ since 0 is the minimizer of (4.1). Hence:

$$\hat{X} = \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(X_\Omega) = A_1 X_\Omega + A_2 (X_\Omega)^2 + A_3 (X_\Omega)^3 + \dots$$

Furthermore, if X_Ω is low-rank (or close to low rank), A_1 goes to identity, and all higher order terms vanish. We can now try to compute expected value:

$$\mathbb{E} \hat{X} = \mathbb{E} \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(X_\Omega) = A_1 X p + A_2 X^2 p^2 + A_3 X^3 p^3 + \dots$$

Here, we have assumed that coefficients A_1, A_2, \dots don't depend on the sampling density. This is not true in general, but let's assume it is, just for illustrative purposes. In this case it makes sense to rectify the procedure:

$$\mathbb{E} \hat{X}' = \mathbb{E} \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(X_\Omega \frac{1}{p}) = A_1 X + A_2 X^2 p + A_3 X^3 p^2 + \dots$$

This kind of rectification was studied before in [19]. Of course, a more general form is

$$\mathbb{E} \hat{X}'' = \mathbb{E} \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(X_\Omega \circ \frac{1}{K})$$

Here, \circ is the Hadamard product – that is, an entry-wise product, and $\frac{1}{K}$ is some matrix.

4.2 Multi-step singular valued decomposition low-rank projection

The single-step SVD matrix completion algorithm can be generalized to an iterative one, as seen in Algorithm 1. From now on we will refer to this algorithm simply by SVD. It will be apparent from the context when we want to talk about actual singular value decomposition instead.

Algorithm 1 Iterative SVD matrix completion algorithm: basic form

- 1: Let H be the original $n \times m$ matrix of rank r to be recovered.
 - 2: Let M be a mutable $n \times m$ array
 - 3:
 - 4: Set $M \leftarrow 0$
 - 5:
 - 6: Set $M_{\Omega} \leftarrow H_{\Omega}$
 - 7: Set $M_{\Omega^{\perp}} \leftarrow \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(M)_{\Omega^{\perp}}$
 - 8:
 - 9: Repeat steps 6-7 until convergence.
-

We can also get rid of Ω^{\perp} , and write a form of the algorithm that is more suggestive about how it should be debiased. See Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Iterative SVD matrix completion algorithm: more suggestive form

- 1: Let H be the original $n \times m$ matrix of rank r to be recovered.
 - 2: Let M be a mutable $n \times m$ array
 - 3:
 - 4: Set $M \leftarrow 0$
 - 5:
 - 6: Set $M \leftarrow \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(M) + (H - \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(M))_{\Omega}$
 - 7:
 - 8: Repeat step 6 until convergence.
-

Note that this algorithm has a different equivalent definition, as shown in Algorithm 3.

It has been shown that this algorithm converges [9] and gives a unique solution. It is also stable in a sense that it won't diverge even if there isn't enough data. For example, we can construct a sampling pattern where only 1/4 is sampled with non-

Algorithm 3 Iterative SVD matrix completion algorithm: more suggestive form

- 1: Let H be the original $n \times m$ matrix of rank r to be recovered.
 - 2: Let M be a mutable $n \times m$ array
 - 3:
 - 4: Set $M \leftarrow 0$
 - 5:
 - 6: Set $M \leftarrow \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(M + (H - M))_{\Omega}$
 - 7:
 - 8: Repeat step 6 until convergence.
-

0	0	0.5061304	0.4938603
0.2	0	1.244009e-15	0.5120501

Table 4.1: Left: sampling densities. Right: Convergence distances. For this experiment a 150×150 matrix was split into 4 equal parts by putting one separator horizontally, and one vertically.

Figure 4.1: Top: convergence distance vs iteration. Bottom: sampling pattern; white means sampled, black means not sampled. Convergence distance was computed for the whole matrix, not just the region with non-zero sampling density, hence the distance doesn't go to zero.

zero probability. In this case, the algorithm can converge on the sampled region. See Table 4.1 and Figure 4.1.

We can debias this SVD algorithm to get version described in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Iterative SVD matrix completion algorithm: more suggestive form

- 1: Let H be the original $n \times m$ matrix of rank r to be recovered.
 - 2: Let M be a mutable $n \times m$ array
 - 3:
 - 4: Set $M \leftarrow 0$
 - 5:
 - 6: Set $M \leftarrow \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(M) + (H - \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(M))_{\Omega} \circ \frac{1}{k}$
 - 7:
 - 8: Repeat step 6 until convergence.
-

Here, as before, $\circ \frac{1}{k}$ is entriwise product (Hadamard product).

4.2.1 Numerical experiments

In this section we will describe more detailed numerical experiments for the SVD algorithm.

First, we need to identify what debiasing parameter k to choose. As we have found out from experiments, rate of convergence of the algorithm as function of debiasing parameter has a single unique minimum. See Figure 4.2, where we have done several trials of computing convergence distance after a fixed number of iterations (100 iterations), as a function of debiasing parameter. For each trial we have takes a different uniform sampling pattern.

We see that debiasing parameter k has a single global minimum, and it is usually slightly larger than the sampling density. Besides that, there are two regions: below the minimum and above the minimum. In the first region, convergence distance rapidly increases, while in the latter one it increases at a much slower rate. In some cases algorithm diverges altogether for small k .

As seen in Figure 4.3, if we fix the sampling pattern, but only vary number of iterations, the function will just get scaled down, without changing the minimum, and the behaviour from two sides away from the minimum. On the other hand, if too many iterations are taken, we run into numerical errors which cause plateaus,

Figure 4.2: SVD: Convergence distance vs debiase value for several samples of sampling pattern of uniform probability. Notice that the optimum is not the same for a fixed p . Also notice that the left branch of each graph has much larger slope than the right branch.

as seen in Figures 4.4 and 4.5. Thus, when running any experiments, we need to make sure that convergence distance doesn't pass a certain threshold (about 10^{-35}) for our results to make any sense.

Continuing the discussion, as can be seen from the plots, debiasing parameter isn't just a function of the sampling density, but also of some other property of sampling pattern, which we were not able to identify. What we were able to identify is that this additional parameter does not in any way depend on first couple of singular value of the sampling pattern matrix, means of rank-1 and rank-2 approximations of sampling pattern, and on row and column deviations from the mean of uniform sampling pattern, see Figures 4.6 and 4.7.

Next, we try to come up with some heuristic as to what the optimal debiase parameter depends on. For the uniform case, we have found that it doesn't seem to

Figure 4.3: SVD: If more iterations are taken, minimum value does not shift.

depend neither on the rank of the matrix, nor on the dimensions of the matrix, and only depends on the sampling density, plus the unidentified parameter. See Figure 4.8.

At first it seems that $n=200, rank=10$ line is different from others, but it's likely that that's actually due to the fact that it takes longer to converge, and since we only did a constant number of steps, the algorithm didn't converge close enough for debiaser to saturate (see Figure 4.5). Hence, we don't take it into account when computing the linear fitting $k = mp + b$.

For the values of the fitting, see Table 4.2. Taking the structure of slopes of convergence rate, as a function of sampling density, we propose the optimal debiaser to be used in practice to be the linear fitting plus the maximum of residuals:

Figure 4.4: SVD: As algorithm converges more and more, it hits a plateau. I think it might be there due to the svd algorithm: it stops when change is too small. Hence, in further experiments, we better make sure we don't hit this region: algorithm needs to terminate before we reach that zone.

$$0.8093p + 0.0791 \quad (4.2)$$

$$0.8093p + 0.0791 + 0.03970094 \quad (4.3)$$

$$0.8093p + 0.1188009 \quad (4.4)$$

Now, as an ansatz, we can try and see if this $0.8093p + 0.1188009$ linear equation for choosing the debiaser that works in most cases with uniform sampling patterns can also be generalized to non-uniform sampling patterns by replacing scalar probability by matrix of probabilities, so that each entry can have different probability: $0.8093P + 0.1188009$.

Furthermore, in practice, we don't usually know the exact distribution of sampling probabilities. Thus, we need to approximate it knowing a single particular

Figure 4.5: SVD: Debiasser minimums vs number of iterations for several samples of sampling patterns.

	SVD	ALS
m	0.8093	0.82895
b	0.0791	0.06037
above	0.03970094	0.05477475
below	-0.0357938	-0.03723244
std	0.01657725	0.01614025

Table 4.2: SVD & ALS: Fitting parameters and residuals statistics. m is the linear coefficient of proportionality, b is a constant bias, above is the maximum of residuals, below is the minimum of residuals, std is standard deviation of residuals.

Figure 4.6: SVD: Correlation of debiaser with first two singular values of sampling pattern, and means of rank-1 and rank-2 approximations of the sampling pattern. $n = 100$, $r = 1$, $p = 0.3$, number of samples = 1000

sampling pattern. As was proposed in [19], this can be done by computing rank-1 approximation of the sampling matrix: $L = \text{Proj}_{rank=1}(\Omega)$.

We can see that this form $0.8093L + 0.1188009$ seems to be good even for non-uniform case. If this is true, then this tells us something about the unknown parameter – it has to be local to each entry. I.e., for each entry, it can only depend on densities along the same row or column. Next, it looks random in the uniform case, following a normal distribution. Therefore, central limit theorem might be somehow involved.

On the other hand, we also need to keep in mind that this random parameter seems to be independent of the overall sampling density. Furthermore, things are invariant to the size of the matrix (and its rank).

Figure 4.7: SVD: Correlation of debiaser with deviation of row and column means from the general mean. $n = 100$, $r = 1$, $p = 0.3$, number of samples = 1000

4.3 Alternating least squares

An alternative approach is based on alternating least squares. It is a bit easier to analyze with the respect to debiaser than the one described in previous section because there is no singular value decomposition involved in the algorithm itself (SVD can still be used to invert non-square matrices, though). The idea is to rewrite (2.1) so that low-rank structure is encoded without the additional restraint:

$$\underset{U, V}{\text{minimize}} \quad \frac{1}{2} \|(UV^T - M)_\Omega\|_{Frob}^2 \quad (4.5)$$

Here U and V are $n \times r$ and $m \times r$ matrices, which encode the low-rank structure of $n \times m$ matrix M . The rows in those matrices, or the whole matrices, are sometimes called latent factors.

The problem in this form does not have an explicit analytic solution, but still

Figure 4.8: SVD: Optimal debiaser as a function of sampling density.

can be solved, for example, with gradient descent. This is not the most efficient way, though. A more efficient way is to iteratively optimize for U and V , as done in Algorithm 5.

Algorithm 5 Alternating least squares matrix completion algorithm

- 1: Let M be the original $n \times m$ matrix of rank r to be recovered.
 - 2: Let U be a mutable $n \times r$ array
 - 3: Let V be a mutable $m \times r$ array
 - 4:
 - 5: Set $V \leftarrow 0$
 - 6: Set $U \leftarrow$ random matrix
 - 7:
 - 8: Set $V \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_V \frac{1}{2} \|(UV^T - M)_\Omega\|_{Frob}^2$
 - 9: Set $U \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_U \frac{1}{2} \|(UV^T - M)_\Omega\|_{Frob}^2$
 - 10:
 - 11: Repeat steps 8-9 until convergence.
-

Steps 8-9 can be solved analytically:

$$V_{n+1}^i = r^{iT} U_n^i (U_n^{iT} U_n^i)^{-1} \quad (4.6)$$

$$U_{n+1}^i = r^i V_n^i (V_n^{iT} V_n^i)^{-1} \quad (4.7)$$

Thinking in the context of movie recommender systems, V^i could encode a particular user, U^i – a particular movie, and r^i – ratings by that user in (4.6), or ratings for that movie in (4.7). This algorithm has provable convergence guarantees [6]. The form of iterative steps in this algorithm is very nice because it is independent for different i 's, and thus it is possible to easily parallelize the algorithm.

One problem with Algorithm 5 is that it involves computation of inverses of lots of small matrices ($U_n^{iT} U_n^i$ and $V_n^{iT} V_n^i$) that overlap in their entries. This makes things inefficient. To address this issue, Fast ALS was developed [9], see Algorithm 6.

In this case, only two matrix inversions per iterations are required, thus speeding things up considerably:

$$V_{n+1} = (M_\Omega + (U_n V_n'^T)_{\Omega^\perp})^T U_n (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} \quad (4.8)$$

$$U_{n+1} = (M_\Omega + (U_n' V_n^T)_{\Omega^\perp}) V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} \quad (4.9)$$

Akin to Algorithm 2, we can rewrite Algorithm in a form that is more suggestive as to how it should be debiased to get Algorithm 7.

We then add a debiaser to it in Algorithm 8. Notice that the form is very similar to Algorithm 4. In this new algorithm, all steps again have an analytic solution:

$$V_{n+1} = (U_n V_n'^T + (M - U_n V_n'^T)_{\Omega} \circ \frac{1}{K})^T U_n (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} \quad (4.10)$$

$$U_{n+1} = (U_n' V_n^T + (M - (U_n' V_n^T))_{\Omega} \circ \frac{1}{K}) V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} \quad (4.11)$$

Now, before going further, it is once again worth analyzing how does this iterative step behave in the sparse regime (that is, when most of the entries of Ω -matrix

Algorithm 6 Fast ALS

- 1: Let M be the original $n \times m$ matrix of rank r to be recovered.
 - 2: Let U, U' be mutable $n \times r$ arrays
 - 3: Let V, V' be mutable $m \times r$ arrays
 - 4:
 - 5: Set $U', V, V' \leftarrow 0$
 - 6: Set $U \leftarrow$ random matrix
 - 7:
 - 8: Set $V' \leftarrow V$
 - 9: Set $V \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_V \frac{1}{2} \|UV^T - (M_\Omega + (UV^T)_{\Omega^\perp})\|_{Frob}^2$
 - 10: Set $U' \leftarrow U$
 - 11: Set $U \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_U \frac{1}{2} \|UV^T - (M_\Omega + (U'V^T)_{\Omega^\perp})\|_{Frob}^2$
 - 12:
 - 13: Repeat steps 8-11 until convergence.
-

Algorithm 7 Fast ALS: more suggestive form

- 1: Let M be the original $n \times m$ matrix of rank r to be recovered.
 - 2: Let U, U' be mutable $n \times r$ arrays
 - 3: Let V, V' be mutable $m \times r$ arrays
 - 4:
 - 5: Set $U', V, V' \leftarrow 0$
 - 6: Set $U \leftarrow$ random matrix
 - 7:
 - 8: Set $V' \leftarrow V$
 - 9: Set $V \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_V \frac{1}{2} \|UV^T - (UV'^T + (M - UV'^T)_\Omega)\|_{Frob}^2$
 - 10: Set $U' \leftarrow U$
 - 11: Set $U \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_U \frac{1}{2} \|UV^T - (U'V^T + (M - U'V^T)_\Omega)\|_{Frob}^2$
 - 12:
 - 13: Repeat steps 8-11 until convergence.
-

are zero, and the dimension of the matrix is on the order of a couple of hundred thousands), which is important for practical applications.

Let's expand the formulas above slightly:

$$V_{n+1} = (V_n' U_n^T U_n + ((M - U_n V_n'^T)_{\Omega} \circ \frac{1}{K})^T U_n) (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} \quad (4.12)$$

$$U_{n+1} = (U_n' V_n^T V_n + (M - (U_n' V_n^T))_{\Omega} \circ \frac{1}{K}) V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} \quad (4.13)$$

One more step:

$$V_{n+1} = V_n' + ((M - U_n V_n'^T)_{\Omega} \circ \frac{1}{K})^T U_n (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} \quad (4.14)$$

$$U_{n+1} = U_n' + ((M - (U_n' V_n^T))_{\Omega} \circ \frac{1}{K}) V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} \quad (4.15)$$

We see that the update step is composed from a sum of a low-rank matrix and a product of sparse and low-rank matrix. Because X_{Ω} term is sparse, the second term in the sum will be sparse too. Furthermore, for the $U_n V_n'^T$ and $U_n' V_n^T$ products in $((M - U_n V_n'^T)_{\Omega})$ and $(M - (U_n' V_n^T))_{\Omega}$, only a sparse number of vector multiplication operations have to be performed. This structure was already explored before in [9].

Algorithm 8 Debiased Fast ALS

- 1: Let M be the original $n \times m$ matrix of rank r to be recovered.
 - 2: Let U, U' be mutable $n \times r$ arrays
 - 3: Let V, V' be mutable $m \times r$ arrays
 - 4:
 - 5: Set $U', V, V' \leftarrow 0$
 - 6: Set $U \leftarrow$ random matrix
 - 7:
 - 8: Set $V' \leftarrow V$
 - 9: Set $V \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_V \frac{1}{2} \|UV^T - (UV'^T + (M - UV'^T)_{\Omega} \circ \frac{1}{K})\|_{Frob}^2$
 - 10: Set $U' \leftarrow U$
 - 11: Set $U \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_U \frac{1}{2} \|UV^T - (U'V^T + (M - U'V^T)_{\Omega} \circ \frac{1}{K})\|_{Frob}^2$
 - 12:
 - 13: Repeat steps 8-11 until convergence.
-

Now, a nice thing about Algorithm 8 is that, unlike the SVD-based Algorithm 4, it allows for easy analytic computation of the debiaser parameter, for arbitrary number of iterations.

For simplicity, let's assume uniform sampling density. In this case, K tensor turns to k scalar, and things simplify somewhat:

$$V_{n+1} = (U_n V_n'^T + (M - U_n V_n'^T)_{\Omega} \frac{1}{k})^T U_n (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} \quad (4.16)$$

$$U_{n+1} = (U_n' V_n^T + (M - (U_n' V_n^T))_{\Omega} \frac{1}{k}) V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} \quad (4.17)$$

Let's also get rid of inverses, subspace projections, and take transpose of the first equation:

$$U_n V_{n+1}^T = U_n V_n'^T + (M - U_n V_n'^T)_{\Omega} \frac{1}{k}$$

$$U_{n+1} V_n^T = U_n' V_n^T + (M - (U_n' V_n^T))_{\Omega} \frac{1}{k}$$

And let's substitute primed matrices by non-primed ones:

$$U_n V_{n+1}^T = U_n V_n^T + (M - U_n V_n^T)_{\Omega} \frac{1}{k}$$

$$U_{n+1} V_n^T = U_n V_n^T + (M - U_n V_n^T)_{\Omega} \frac{1}{k}$$

Re-arranging the terms:

$$U_n (V_{n+1}^T - V_n^T) = (M - U_n V_n^T)_{\Omega} \frac{1}{k} \quad (4.18)$$

$$(U_{n+1} - U_n) V_n^T = (M - U_n V_n^T)_{\Omega} \frac{1}{k} \quad (4.19)$$

We see that k is a coefficient of proportionality between the two expressions above. Now let's try back substitution on the original expression:

$$V_{n+1} = (U_n V_n^T + (M - U_n V_n^T) \Omega \frac{1}{k})^T U_n (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} \quad (4.20)$$

$$U_{n+1} = (U_n V_n^T + (M - (U_n V_n^T)) \Omega \frac{1}{k}) V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} \quad (4.21)$$

We see that to proceed we need to compute $U_n V_n^T$, $U_n^T U_n$, and $V_n^T V_n$ terms. Let's work systematically:

$$V_{n+1}^T = (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} U_n^T (U_n V_n^T + (M - U_n V_n^T) \Omega \frac{1}{k}) \quad (4.22)$$

$$U_{n+1}^T = (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} V_n (U_n V_n^T + (M - (U_n V_n^T)) \Omega \frac{1}{k})^T \quad (4.23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} U_{n+1} V_{n+1}^T &= (U_n V_n^T + (M - (U_n V_n^T)) \Omega \frac{1}{k}) V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} \\ &\quad (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} U_n^T (U_n V_n^T + (M - U_n V_n^T) \Omega \frac{1}{k}) \end{aligned} \quad (4.24)$$

This simplifies somewhat:

$$\begin{aligned} U_{n+1} V_{n+1}^T &= (U_n + (M - (U_n V_n^T)) \Omega V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} \frac{1}{k}) \\ &\quad (V_n^T + (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} U_n^T (M - U_n V_n^T) \Omega \frac{1}{k}) \end{aligned} \quad (4.25)$$

Let's expand this:

$$\begin{aligned} U_{n+1} V_{n+1}^T &= U_n V_n^T + (M - (U_n V_n^T)) \Omega V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} V_n^T \frac{1}{k} + \\ &\quad + U_n (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} U_n^T (M - U_n V_n^T) \Omega \frac{1}{k} + \\ &\quad + (M - (U_n V_n^T)) \Omega V_n (V_n^T V_n)^{-1} (U_n^T U_n)^{-1} U_n^T (M - U_n V_n^T) \Omega \frac{1}{k^2} \end{aligned} \quad (4.26)$$

In the debiased regime, we want $\mathbb{E}U_nV_n^T = M$, for all n . Thus, taking expected value of equation above, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= \mathbb{E}(M - (U_nV_n^T))_{\Omega}V_n(V_n^TV_n)^{-1}V_n^T\frac{1}{k} + \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E}U_n(U_n^TU_n)^{-1}U_n^T(M - U_nV_n^T)_{\Omega}\frac{1}{k} + \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E}(M - (U_nV_n^T))_{\Omega}V_n(V_n^TV_n)^{-1}(U_n^TU_n)^{-1}U_n^T(M - U_nV_n^T)_{\Omega}\frac{1}{k^2} \quad (4.27)
\end{aligned}$$

Thus:

$$\begin{aligned}
&(\mathbb{E}(M - (U_nV_n^T))_{\Omega}V_n(V_n^TV_n)^{-1}V_n^T + \mathbb{E}U_n(U_n^TU_n)^{-1}U_n^T(M - U_nV_n^T)_{\Omega})k = \\
&= \mathbb{E}(M - (U_nV_n^T))_{\Omega}V_n(V_n^TV_n)^{-1}(U_n^TU_n)^{-1}U_n^T(M - U_nV_n^T)_{\Omega} \quad (4.28)
\end{aligned}$$

And we once again get k as a coefficient of proportionality between two quantities. In theory, we can proceed the same way in order to find exact analytical formula for k . Perhaps we should try back substituting for larger and larger n , and seeing how the optimal k change. This will generate a sequence, and a limit of that sequence would be the exact debiaser k . It should be possible to do this in a computer algebra system. In fact, this should allow us to reproduce Figure 4.10, and pretty much all other experimental results for the ALS algorithm. Given that the general shape of debiasers seems to be the same for ALS and SVD algorithms, this should also shed light onto how the debiaser works with the SVD algorithm.

4.3.1 Numerical experiments

First, let's analyze how does algorithm behave for different debiaser parameters. We start with uniform case. As can be seen from Figure 4.12, convergence results are quite noisy. This could be due to the fact that in Fast ALS, initial guess is chosen randomly. Hence, for the ease of exploration, we choose a warm start by computing the closest rank- r approximation to the zero padded version of input matrix (that is, the one-step algorithm, $\hat{X} = \text{Proj}_{\text{rank}=r}(X_{\Omega})$).

Figure 4.9: ALS: Convergence distance vs debiase value for several samples of sampling pattern of uniform probability. Using warm start, curves become much smoother. Still can see the plateau caused by numerical errors, so need to be careful to avoid it.

This results in Figure 4.9. As we can see from it, the picture is very similar to the SVD case. Next, we can study how does the optimal debiase parameter varies as we take more iterations. This can be seen in Figure 4.10. This doesn't look much different from Figure 4.5, so it means the theory behind behavior of both algorithm with respect to different debiase parameters should be similar.

Now, we can do the same thing that we did with SVD algorithm: analyze dependence of debiasing parameter versus sampling density for uniform case, see Figure 4.11 and Table 4.2. We see that results are very close to the SVD case. The proposed heuristic for optimal parameter for ALS case is:

Figure 4.10: ALS: Optimal debiaser vs number of iterations.

$$0.82895p + 0.06037 \quad (4.29)$$

$$0.82895p + 0.06037 + 0.05477475 \quad (4.30)$$

$$0.82895p + 0.1151447 \quad (4.31)$$

As we see, results for SVD and ALS case are very similar:

$$0.8093p + 0.1188009 \quad (\text{SVD}) \quad (4.32)$$

$$0.82895p + 0.1151447 \quad (\text{ALS}) \quad (4.33)$$

Taking into account the fact that we only have about 200 measurements for each formula, there are exactly identical.

We now proceed to a benchmark test with MovieLens data. We are using 25M MovieLens dataset [7], with max rank set to 100 and to 50, so that our results can

Figure 4.11: ALS: Optimal debiaser as a function of sampling density.

vanilla	0.000154746
debiased	0.0001319378
debiased (constant)	0.0001317157
base	0.0001219378

Table 4.3: ALS-movielens: Final convergence values, and the base offset.

Base offset is there to make the log version of the plot nicer. debiased (scalar) is the same as debiased, but a median of rank-1 approximation of sampling matrix is taken instead of the actual rank-1 approximation

be compared with right plot in Figure 3 in [9]. See Figure 4.13. Final convergence values are shown in Table 4.3. Since neither of the algorithms converge to zero (this could be partially due to the fact that the MovieLens matrix is only approximately low-rank), we had to apply a base shift when displaying the log plot. Base shift is recorded in the table. Furthermore, to compute the convergence distances, it was unpractical and impossible to compute it based on all the entries of the completed matrix.

Figure 4.12: ALS: Convergence distance vs debiser value for several samples of sampling pattern of uniform probability. Like in the SVD case, optimum is not the same for a fixed p . Also notice that the left branch of each graph has much larger slope than the right branch. We thus can use the maximum of these as a debiser value for a fixed p . On the other hand, we can try other things too. Like use first two singular values of sampling pattern instead of sampling density. A difference from SVD case is that things are very noisy: this is due to the random initial guess. If we use SVD-based warm start, then the noise disappears.

First, it is unpractical because the matrix is 162541×209171 , and that makes 33998863511 numbers to be computed, which overall take more than 100G of space. Even if we had that much RAM, it would still take a substantial amount of time to compute all those entries. Second, the movielens matrix is not complete, and the unknown entries are actually unknown. We could have gone around this issue by generation our own low-rank matrix, and then only using the sampling pattern from movielens, but then again it wouldn't be a good idea to compute the distance based on all entries for the first reason.

Figure 4.13: Debiased (matrix&scalar debiased) vs non-debiased ALS, performed on the movielens dataset, with maxrank set to 100, and lambda to 50.

Therefore, to compute the distance we only use the measured entries, which are sparse (in fact, there are 25000095 entries known, this makes the sparsity of 0.000735321). Furthermore, we normalize the result by dividing in by the square root of the number of entries. What we have not done is to make it so that the ratings are centered at zero, and the spread around each column to be one. This could explain the discrepancy of about 10 with our result and [9] for the non-debiased ALS algorithm.

Besides that, to make the algorithm to work, we had to ramp up the constant bias in the linear debiased heuristic somewhat, to get: $0.82895L + 0.4$ (previously, it was about $0.82895L + 0.12$). For all smaller biases, algorithm diverges. Since the bias of 0.4 is so high, it is interesting to analyze L (the rank-1 approximation of sampling pattern), to see how much does the non-constant term contribute, see Figure 4.14. First of all, the algorithm diverges if we simply ignore the non-constant

Figure 4.14: Histogram of values of rank-1 approximation of sampling pattern for the MovieLens dataset.

part, and set the debiaser to 0.4. But it does converge, and in fact converges slightly better, if we replace L by median value of L . It could be that this is just a statistical artifact: median value makes most of the entries fit better, and there is less influence from the unidentified parameter. More research is needed to identify the reasons.

4.4 Comparison of debiased SVD and debiased Fast ALS algorithms

Non-debiased versions of SVD and ALS algorithms seem to have quite similar convergence rates, with ALS being only slightly faster (but on the same order of magnitude). Here, “faster” means convergence distance vs fixed number of iterations, but when talking about these algorithms it is also important to consider the time spent per each iteration.

In this case, ALS is a lot faster since it doesn’t require a computation of a low-

Figure 4.15: SVD, ALS + debias: sample 1

	sample 1	sample 2	sample 3
vanilla SVD	0.0001830918	0.0003712561	0.000622019
vanilla ALS	0.0001294567	0.0003162862	0.0004631788
debiased SVD	9.921039e-08	1.282154e-08	1.673999e-08
debiased ALS	3.81552e-12	1.292068e-08	2.590908e-09

Table 4.4: Synthetic data set: Convergence distance after 100 steps for SVD, ALS, and their debiased versions. Three samples are taken. $n=200$, $r=1$, sampling pattern=1-1-1-1, $p_{00}=0.2$, $p_{01}=0.3$, $p_{10}=0.1$, $p_{11}=0.4$.

rank projection of some low-rank plus sparse matrix. Instead, only an update of a previous estimate of a latent factor is needed (latent factors are the two matrices from which a low-rank matrix is constructed).

This is especially important for the case of large sparse matrices, like the one that comes from real world benchmarks like the movielens dataset. In fact, softImpute uses an ALS-based approach to compute the SVD in the sparse-SVD version of the algorithm. I.e. each step of SVD algorithm is equivalent for a number of

Figure 4.16: SVD, ALS + debias: sample 2

steps of ALS algorithm. This makes things quite slow.

That's why, to compare the two algorithms, we would use a benchmark with synthetic data, for a relatively small 200×200 matrix, split into 4 parts (1-1-1-1, as described in the Methods chapter). Furthermore, we run three trials because it appears that behaviour of debiased versions of algorithms is quite variant, even for the same fixed sampling densities. See Figures 4.15, 4.16, 4.17 and Table 4.4. From these plots and the table, we can see that it sometimes debiased ALS algorithm can perform 10000 times better than the SVD counterpart, and at other times it performs slightly slower ($1.282154e-08$ vs $1.292068e-08$), but on the same order of magnitude.

Figure 4.17: SVD, ALS + debias: sample 3

Chapter 5

Conclusion and Future Work

We have demonstrated the use of debiasing technique on two simple matrix completion algorithms. One is iterative low-rank and feasible-space projections, and another is alternative least squares.

Both algorithms are very similar in nature: one tries to find the closest low-rank matrix to the sum of zero-padded matrix of known entries, plus the previous guess for unknown entries. The other algorithm tries to do essentially the same, but instead of finding a new low-rank matrix each step, it instead maintains two factors from which the low-rank matrix is build. And, instead of computing a low-rank approximation each time, it updates the two low-rank factors separately. This in turn makes it much faster and scalable.

We explained how the debiasing is done and what pattern to look for when using it. This in turn should make it easier to expand debiasing framework for a larger set of algorithms. First we explored the uniform case, in which debiasing parameter turns to a simple scalar value. We demonstrated that algorithm convergence rate as a function of debiasing parameter, has a single minimum, a small slope for values above the minimum, and large slope for the values above the minimum. This is important because it shows that algorithms will diverge if debiasing parameter is too small. Furthermore, the exact form of this function depends not only on sampling density, but also on some unidentified parameters. We have found that this pattern is the same for both algorithms that were studied.

We have tries to come up with empirical heuristic as to what the optimal de-

biasing parameter should be. Doing so, we have found that this parameter doesn't seem to depend neither on the rank, nor the dimensions of the matrix, and in uniform case, only depend on sampling density, plus some unidentified parameter. We have found that for our sampling method, debiasing parameter is a linear function of sampling density, plus unidentified parameter, which seems to follow a normal distribution. Once again, this was true for both algorithms, and did not depend neither on rank, nor the dimensions of the matrix.

Then, to construct a heuristic that can be used in practice, we have computed the shape of the mean values of optimal debiasers, treating unknown parameter as noise, and then shifted the line up, so that all of the entries sampled in the experiments can converge.

We then test if this simple linear form of debiasing parameter extends to non-uniform sampling patterns, by simply replacing probability scalar by probability matrix. We test it on real-world movielens benchmark dataset, using previously suggested rank-1 sampling matrix projection to approximate sampling density. Since SVD based algorithm is very inefficient for datasets of that size, we have only tested this on Fast ALS. We demonstrate that in some cases, debiased algorithm performs better with the simple heuristic that we have found.

5.1 Future Work

There are a number of loose ends that can be tied up:

- We can try to analytically find optimal debiaser for the Fast ALS algorithm due to the simple structure of iterative step.
- The “unknown parameter” should be identified. As our work suggests, more accurate heuristics can give at least a couple of orders of magnitude speedups if minimum is matched correctly.
- We can test the algorithm on larger datasets, for example, Netflix. Authors of softImpute have the codes for doing so in a distributed environment [9], so we simply have to modify them and run on a cluster.
- Split the data into training/testing to see if algorithms over fit. This might

help decide if there is actually an improvement in using non-constant debi-
aser (see MovieLens-related discussion above).

Bibliography

- [1] P. Bhavana, V. Kumar, and V. Padmanabhan. Block based singular value decomposition approach to matrix factorization for recommender systems, 2019. → pages 7
- [2] E. J. Candès and T. Tao. The power of convex relaxation: Near-optimal matrix completion. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 56(5): 2053–2080, 2010. → pages 5
- [3] G. Csardi and T. Nepusz. The igraph software package for complex network research. *InterJournal, Complex Systems*:1695, 2006. URL <http://igraph.org>. → pages 9
- [4] M. Gallagher, C. Tygh, J. Urschel, and L. Zikatanov. Graph drawing in spectral layout. → pages 3
- [5] D. Gross, Y.-K. Liu, S. T. Flammia, S. Becker, and J. Eisert. Quantum state tomography via compressed sensing. *Physical Review Letters*, 105(15), Oct 2010. ISSN 1079-7114. doi:10.1103/physrevlett.105.150401. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.105.150401>. → pages 2
- [6] S. Gunasekar, A. Acharya, N. Gaur, and J. Ghosh. Noisy matrix completion using alternating minimization. In H. Blockeel, K. Kersting, S. Nijssen, and F. Železný, editors, *Machine Learning and Knowledge Discovery in Databases*, pages 194–209, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2013. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. ISBN 978-3-642-40991-2. → pages 24
- [7] F. M. Harper and J. A. Konstan. The movielens datasets: History and context. *ACM Trans. Interact. Intell. Syst.*, 5(4), Dec. 2015. ISSN 2160-6455. doi:10.1145/2827872. URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/2827872>. → pages 31
- [8] T. Hastie and R. Mazumder. *softImpute: Matrix Completion via Iterative Soft-Thresholded SVD*, 2015. URL

<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=softImpute>. R package version 1.4. → pages 9

- [9] T. Hastie, R. Mazumder, J. Lee, and R. Zadeh. Matrix completion and low-rank svd via fast alternating least squares, 2014. → pages 7, 9, 14, 24, 26, 32, 34, 40
- [10] J. Josse, S. Sardy, and S. Wager. *denoiseR: Regularized Low Rank Matrix Estimation*, 2020. URL <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=denoiseR>. R package version 1.0.2. → pages 9
- [11] Y. Koren, R. Bell, and C. Volinsky. Matrix factorization techniques for recommender systems. *Computer*, 42(8):30–37, 2009. → pages 2
- [12] J. D. Lee, B. Recht, N. Srebro, J. Tropp, and R. R. Salakhutdinov. Practical large-scale optimization for max-norm regularization. In J. D. Lafferty, C. K. I. Williams, J. Shawe-Taylor, R. S. Zemel, and A. Culotta, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 23*, pages 1297–1305. Curran Associates, Inc., 2010. URL <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/4124-practical-large-scale-optimization-for-max-norm-regularization.pdf>. → pages 7
- [13] T. Mikolov, I. Sutskever, K. Chen, G. S. Corrado, and J. Dean. Distributed representations of words and phrases and their compositionality. In C. J. C. Burges, L. Bottou, M. Welling, Z. Ghahramani, and K. Q. Weinberger, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 26*, pages 3111–3119. Curran Associates, Inc., 2013. URL <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/5021-distributed-representations-of-words-and-phrases-and-their-compositionality.pdf>. → pages 2
- [14] M. Newman. Power laws, pareto distributions and zipf’s law. *Contemporary Physics*, 46(5):323–351, Sep 2005. ISSN 1366-5812. doi:10.1080/00107510500052444. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00107510500052444>. → pages 1
- [15] V. Novaković and S. Singer. An implicit hari–zimmermann algorithm for the generalized svd on the gpus, 2019. → pages 7
- [16] R Core Team. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, 2019. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>. → pages 9

- [17] S. Redner. How popular is your paper? an empirical study of the citation distribution. *The European Physical Journal B*, 4(2):131–134, Aug 1998. ISSN 1434-6028. doi:10.1007/s100510050359. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s100510050359>. → pages 1
- [18] D. Schoch. *graphlayouts: Additional Layout Algorithms for Network Visualizations*, 2020. URL <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=graphlayouts>. R package version 0.6.0. → pages 9
- [19] Y. P. M. W. Simon Foucart, Deanna Needell. De-biasing low-rank projection for matrix completion, 2017. URL <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2275004>. → pages 8, 12, 13, 21
- [20] M. Sorbaro, J. M. Herrmann, and M. H. Hennig. Statistical models of neural activity, criticality, and zipf’s law, 2018. → pages 1
- [21] N. Srebro, J. Rennie, and T. S. Jaakkola. Maximum-margin matrix factorization. In L. K. Saul, Y. Weiss, and L. Bottou, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 17*, pages 1329–1336. MIT Press, 2005. URL <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/2655-maximum-margin-matrix-factorization.pdf>. → pages 7
- [22] Q. Yao, X. Chen, J. Kwok, and Y. Li. Efficient neural interaction functions search for collaborative filtering, 01 2020. → pages 3

Appendix A

Modified softImpute package code

For the ease of reproduction, we can release modified softImpute package as a publicly-available R package. Furthermore, we can share all the analysis codes on github, and even pack them nicely into an isolated docker container (and upload to dockerhub) with all the dependencies and libraries frozen. Nevertheless, in this section we will briefly list modified code as an illustration to how algorithms should be debiased.

In the later code, look for `debias.matrix` to find out parts that are affected by debiasing.

Listing A.1: softImpute/R/softImpute.R: polymorphic function that calls other functions depending on the type of the matrix (sparse or dense), and algorithm requested.

```
softImpute=function(x, rank.max = 2, lambda=0,
  type=c("als", "svd"), thresh =
  1e-30, maxit=400, trace.it=FALSE, warm.start=NULL, final.svd=TRUE,
  orig_matrix=NULL, debias.matrix=NULL) {
  if(rank.max > (rmax<-min(dim(x))-1)) {
    rank.max=rmax
    warning(paste("rank.max should not exceed
      min(dim(x))-1; changed to ", rmax))
```

```

    }
    this.call=match.call()
    type=match.arg(type)
    warm.start=clean.warm.start(warm.start)# build in some
        protection here for bad warm starts
    fit=softImpute.x(x, J=rank.max,lambda,type,
        thresh,maxit,trace.it,warm.start,final.svd,
        orig_matrix, debias.matrix)
    attr(fit,"call")=this.call
    fit
  }
softImpute.x.matrix=function(x, J,lambda,type,
  thresh,maxit,trace.it,warm.start,final.svd,
  orig_matrix, debias.matrix){
  switch(type,
    "als"=simpute.als(x, J,thresh,
      lambda,maxit,trace.it,warm.start,final.svd,
      orig_matrix, debias.matrix),
    "svd"=simpute.svd(x, J,thresh,
      lambda,maxit,trace.it,warm.start,final.svd,
      orig_matrix, debias.matrix)
  )
}
softImpute.x.Incomplete=function(x, J,lambda,type,
  thresh,maxit,trace.it,warm.start,final.svd,
  orig_matrix, debias.matrix){
  switch(type,
    "als"=Ssimpute.als(x, J,thresh,
      lambda,maxit,trace.it,warm.start,final.svd,
      orig_matrix, debias.matrix),
    "svd"=Ssimpute.svd(x, J,thresh,
      lambda,maxit,trace.it,warm.start,final.svd,
      orig_matrix, debias.matrix)
  )
}

setGeneric("softImpute.x",softImpute.x.matrix)
setMethod("softImpute.x","Incomplete",softImpute.x.Incomplete)

```

Listing A.2: softImpute/R/simpute.svd.R: SVD based algorithm for dense matrices

```

simpute.svd <-
  function (x, J = 2, thresh =
    1e-30, lambda=0, maxit=10000, trace.it=FALSE, warm.start=NULL,
    final.svd=TRUE, orig_matrix=NULL, debias.matrix=NULL)
  {
    this.call=match.call()
    a=names(attributes(x))
    binames=c("biScale:row", "biScale:column")
    if(all(match(binames, a, FALSE))){
      biats=attributes(x)[binames]
    } else biats=NULL
    n <- dim(x)
    m <- n[2]
    n <- n[1]
    xnas <- is.na(x)

    nz=m*n-sum(xnas)
    xfill <- x
    xfill[xnas] <- 0
    if(!is.null(warm.start)){
      ###must have u, d and v components
      if(!all(match(c("u", "d", "v"), names(warm.start), 0)>0)) stop("warm.start
        does not have components u, d and v")
      D=warm.start$d
      nzD=sum(D>0)
      JD=min(nzD, J)
      U=warm.start$u[, seq(JD), drop=FALSE]
      V=warm.start$v[, seq(JD), drop=FALSE]
      D=D[seq(JD)]
      xhat=U%*(D*t(V))
      xfill[xnas] <- xhat[xnas]
    }
    svd.xfill=svds(xfill, J)
    terminator <- 1
    iter <- 0
    if (trace.it) {
      logger <- matrix(data=NA, nrow=maxit, ncol=1)
    }
  }

```

```

}

#start.time <- Sys.time()
d=svd.xfill$d
d=pmax(d-lambda,0)
xtemp <- svd.xfill$u[, seq(J)] %*% (d[seq(J)] *
  t(svd.xfill$v[,seq(J)]))
distance <- frobenius.norm(orig_matrix - xtemp)

while ((distance > thresh)&(iter<maxit)) {
#while (iter<maxit) {
  iter <- iter + 1
  svd.old=svd.xfill
  d=svd.xfill$d
  d=pmax(d-lambda,0)
  xhat <- svd.xfill$u %*% (d * t(svd.xfill$v))
  if (!is.null(debias.matrix)) {
    xfill[!xnas] <- xhat[!xnas] + (x[!xnas] -
      xhat[!xnas])*debias.matrix
    xfill[xnas] <- xhat[xnas]
  }
  else {
    xfill[xnas] <- xhat[xnas]
  }
  svd.xfill=svds(xfill, J)

  xtemp <- svd.xfill$u[, seq(J)] %*% (d[seq(J)] *
    t(svd.xfill$v[,seq(J)]))
  distance <- frobenius.norm(orig_matrix - xtemp)
  if (trace.it) {
    logger[iter] <- distance
  }
}
d=pmax(svd.xfill$d-lambda,0)
J=min(sum(d>0)+1,J)
svd.xfill=list(u=svd.xfill$u, d=d, v=svd.xfill$v)
#if(iter==maxit)warning(paste("Convergence not achieved
  by",maxit,"iterations"))
xtemp <- svd.xfill$u %*% (d * t(svd.xfill$v))
if (!is.null(debias.matrix)) {

```

```

xtemp[!xnas] <- xtemp[!xnas] + (x[!xnas] -
  xtemp[!xnas])*debias.matrix
}
if (trace.it) {
  attributes(svd.xfill)=c(attributes(svd.xfill),list(lambda=lambda,call=this.call,
    distance=frobenius.norm(orig_matrix - xtemp),
    result=xtemp, iter=iter, logger=logger),biats)
} else {
  attributes(svd.xfill)=c(attributes(svd.xfill),list(lambda=lambda,call=this.call,
    distance=frobenius.norm(orig_matrix - xtemp),
    result=xtemp, iter=iter),biats)
}
}
svd.xfill
}

```

Listing A.3: softImpute/R/simpute.als.R: ALS based algorithm for dense matrices

```

simpute.als<-function (x, J = 2, thresh =
  1e-05,lambda=0,maxit=100,trace.it=TRUE,
  warm.start=NULL, final.svd=TRUE, orig_matrix=NULL,
  debias.matrix=NULL)
{### x is a matrix, possibly with NAs
  n <- dim(x)
  m <- n[2]
  n <- n[1]
  this.call=match.call()
  a=names(attributes(x))
  binames=c("biScale:row","biScale:column")
  if(all(match(binames,a,FALSE))){
    biats=attributes(x)[binames]
  } else biats=NULL

  xnas <- is.na(x)
  nz=m*n-sum(xnas)
  xfill <- x
  if(!is.null(warm.start)){
    #must have u,d and v components
    if(!all(match(c("u","d","v"),names(warm.start),0)>0))stop("warm.start

```

```

        does not have components u, d and v")
warm=TRUE
D=warm.start$d
JD=sum(D>0)
if (JD >= J) {
  U=warm.start$u[, seq(J), drop=FALSE]
  V=warm.start$v[, seq(J), drop=FALSE]
  Dsq=D[seq(J)]
}
else{
  Dsq=c(D, rep(D[JD], J-JD))
  Ja=J-JD
  U=warm.start$u
  Ua=matrix(rnorm(n*Ja), n, Ja)
  Ua=Ua-U%*% (t(U)%*%Ua)
  Ua=svd(Ua)$u
  U=cbind(U, Ua)
  V=cbind(warm.start$v, matrix(0, m, Ja))
}
xfill[xnas]=(U%*%(Dsq*t(V)))[xnas]
}
else
{
  V=matrix(0, m, J)
  U=matrix(rnorm(n*J), n, J)
  U=svd(U)$u
  Dsq=rep(1, J) # we call it Dsq because A=UD and B=VD and
                AB'=U Dsq V^T
  xfill[xnas]=0
}

#if (trace.it) {
logger <- matrix(data=NA, nrow=maxit, ncol=1)
#}

ratio <- 1
iter <- 0
while ((ratio > thresh)&(iter<maxit)) {
  iter <- iter + 1

```

```

U.old=U
V.old=V
Dsq.old=Dsq
## U step
B=t(U)%*%xfill
if(lambda>0)B=B*(Dsq/(Dsq+lambda))
Bsvd=svd(t(B))
V=Bsvd$u
Dsq=(Bsvd$d)
U=U%*%Bsvd$v
xhat=U %*%(Dsq*t(V))

if (!is.null(debias.matrix)) {
  xfill[!xnas] <- xhat[!xnas] + (x[!xnas] -
    xhat[!xnas])*debias.matrix
  xfill[xnas] <- xhat[xnas]
} else {
  xfill[xnas] <- xhat[xnas]
}

###The next line we could have done later; this is to match
with sparse version
if(trace.it) obj=(.5*sum(
  (xfill-xhat)[!xnas]^2)+lambda*sum(Dsq))/nz
## V step
A=t(xfill%*%V)
if(lambda>0)A=A*(Dsq/(Dsq+lambda))
Asvd=svd(t(A))
U=Asvd$u
Dsq=Asvd$d
V=V %*% Asvd$v
xhat=U %*%(Dsq*t(V))
if (!is.null(debias.matrix)) {
  xfill[!xnas] <- xhat[!xnas] + (x[!xnas] -
    xhat[!xnas])*debias.matrix
  xfill[xnas] <- xhat[xnas]
} else {
  xfill[xnas] <- xhat[xnas]
}
#xfill[xnas]=xhat[xnas]

```

```

#ratio=Frob(U.old,Dsq.old,V.old,U,Dsq,V)
#if(trace.it) cat(iter, ":",
    "obj",format(round(obj,5)),"ratio", ratio, "\n")

if (!is.null(orig_matrix)) {
  if (trace.it) {
    distance <- frobenius.norm(orig_matrix - xfill)
    logger[iter] <- distance
  }
}

# if(iter==maxit)warning(paste("Convergence not achieved
# by",maxit,"iterations"))

if(lambda>0&final.svd){
  U=xfill%*%V
  sU=svd(U)
  U=sU$u
  Dsq=sU$d
  V=V%*%sU$v
  Dsq=pmax(Dsq-lambda,0)
  if(trace.it){
    xhat=U %*% (Dsq*t(V))
    obj=(.5*sum( (xfill-xhat) [!xnas]^2)+lambda*sum(Dsq))/nz
    cat("final SVD:", "obj",format(round(obj,5)),"\n")
  }
}

J=min(sum(Dsq>0)+1,J)
out=list(u=U[,seq(J)],d=Dsq[seq(J)],v=V[,seq(J)])
if (!is.null(orig_matrix)) {
  distance <- frobenius.norm(orig_matrix - xfill)
  attributes(out)=c(attributes(out),list(lambda=lambda,call=this.call,
    logger=logger, distance=distance),biats)
} else {
  attributes(out)=c(attributes(out),list(lambda=lambda,call=this.call,
    logger=logger),biats)
}
out

```

```
}  
}
```

Listing A.4: softImpute/R/Ssimpute.svd.R: SVD based algorithm for sparse matrices

```
Ssimpute.svd <-  
  function (x, J = 2, thresh =  
    1e-05, lambda=0, maxit=100, trace.it=FALSE, warm.start=NULL,  
    final.svd=TRUE, orig_matrix=NULL, debias.matrix=NULL)  
  {  
    ###This function expects an object of class "Incomplete" which  
      inherits from "sparseMatrix", where the missing entries  
      ##are replaced with zeros. If it was centered, then it  
      carries the centering info with it  
    this.call=match.call()  
    a=names(attributes(x))  
    binames=c("biScale:row", "biScale:column")  
    if(all(match(binames, a, FALSE))){  
      biats=attributes(x)[binames]  
    } else biats=NULL  
  
    if(!inherits(x, "dgCMatrix")) x=as(x, "dgCMatrix")  
    irow=x@i  
    pcol=x@p  
    n <- dim(x)  
    m <- n[2]  
    n <- n[1]  
    nz=nnzero(x)  
    xres=x  
    if(!is.null(warm.start)){  
      ###must have u, d and v components  
      if(!all(match(c("u", "d", "v"), names(warm.start), 0)>0)) stop("warm.start  
        does not have components u, d and v")  
      D=warm.start$d  
      nzD=sum(D>0)  
      JD=min(nzD, J)  
      U=warm.start$u[, seq(JD), drop=FALSE]  
      V=warm.start$v[, seq(JD), drop=FALSE]
```

```

D=D[seq(JD)]
BD=UD(V,D,m)
xhat.Omega=suC(U,BD,irow,pcol)
xres@x=x@x-xhat.Omega
xfill=splr(xres,U,BD)
svd.xfill=Ssvd.als(xfill,J,thresh,lambda,maxit,trace.it,warm.start=list(u=U,d=D,v=V)
}
else {
xfill=x
svd.xfill=Ssvd.als(xfill,J,thresh,lambda,maxit,trace.it)
}
ratio <- 1
iter <- 0

logger <- matrix(data=NA,nrow=maxit,ncol=1)
while ((ratio > thresh)&(iter<maxit)) {
iter <- iter + 1
svd.old=svd.xfill
BD=UD(svd.xfill$v,svd.xfill$d,m)
U=svd.xfill$u
xhat.Omega=suC(U,BD,irow,pcol)
if (!is.null(debias.matrix)) {
xres@x=(x@x-xhat.Omega)*debias.matrix
} else {
xres@x=x@x-xhat.Omega
}
xfill=splr(xres,U,BD)
svd.xfill=Ssvd.als(xfill,J,thresh,lambda,maxit,trace.it,warm.start=svd.xfill)
ratio=Frob(svd.old$u,svd.old$d,svd.old$v,svd.xfill$u,svd.xfill$d,svd.xfill$v)

distance <- norm((xres@x)/length(x@x), type="2")
logger[iter] <- distance
if(trace.it){
obj=(.5*sum(xres@x^2)+lambda*sum(svd.old$d))/nz
cat(iter, ":", "obj", format(round(obj,5)), "ratio", ratio,
"distance", distance, "\n")
}
}
if(iter==maxit)warning(paste("Convergence not achieved
by",maxit,"iterations"))

```

```

###Final cleanup of svd
A=xfill%*%svd.xfill$v
Asvd=svd(A)
U=Asvd$u
Dsq=Asvd$d
V=svd.xfill$v %*% Asvd$v
Dsq=pmax(Dsq-lambda,0)
###
J=min(sum(Dsq>0)+1,J)
svd.xfill=list(u=U[, seq(J)], d=Dsq[seq(J)], v=V[,seq(J)])
  attributes(svd.xfill)=c(attributes(svd.xfill),list(lambda=lambda,call=this.call,
    logger=logger),biats)
svd.xfill
}

```

Listing A.5: softImpute/R/Ssimpute.als.R: ALS based algorithm for sparse matrices

```

Ssimpute.als <-
function(x, J = 2, thresh =
  1e-05, lambda=0, maxit=100, trace.it=FALSE, warm.start=NULL, final.svd=TRUE,
  orig_matrix=NULL, debias.matrix=NULL)
{
  ###This function expects an object of class "Incomplete"
    which inherits from "sparseMatrix", where the missing
    entries
  ###are replaced with zeros. If it was centered, then it
    carries the centering info with it
  this.call=match.call()
  a=names(attributes(x))
  binames=c("biScale:row", "biScale:column")
  if(all(match(binames, a, FALSE))){
    biats=attributes(x)[binames]
  } else biats=NULL

  if(!inherits(x, "dgCMatrix"))x=as(x, "dgCMatrix")
  irow=x@i
  pcol=x@p
  n <- dim(x)

```

```

m <- n[2]
n <- n[1]
nz=nnzero(x)
warm=FALSE

# debias
#debias.m <- svd.als((x != 0),rank=1,trace=TRUE)
#debias.m <- suvC(U,BD,irow,pcol)
if(!is.null(warm.start)){
  #must have u,d and v components
  if(!all(match(c("u","d","v"),names(warm.start),0)>0))stop("warm.start
    does not have components u, d and v")
  warm=TRUE
  D=warm.start$d
  JD=sum(D>0)
  if(JD >= J){
    U=warm.start$u[,seq(J),drop=FALSE]
    V=warm.start$v[,seq(J),drop=FALSE]
    Dsq=D[seq(J)]
  }
  else{
    Dsq=c(D,rep(D[JD],J-JD))
    Ja=J-JD
    U=warm.start$u
    Ua=matrix(rnorm(n*Ja),n,Ja)
    Ua=Ua-U%*% (t(U)%*%Ua)
    Ua=svd(Ua)$u
    U=cbind(U,Ua)
    V=cbind(warm.start$v,matrix(0,m,Ja))
  }
}
else
{
  V=matrix(0,m,J)
  U=matrix(rnorm(n*J),n,J)
  U=svd(U)$u
  Dsq=rep(1,J) # we call it Dsq because A=UD and B=VD and
  AB'=U Dsq V^T
}
ratio <- 1

```

```

iter <- 0
xres=x

logger <- matrix(data=NA,nrow=maxit,ncol=1)
while ((ratio > thresh)&(iter<maxit)) {
  iter <- iter + 1
  U.old=U
  V.old=V
  Dsq.old=Dsq
  ## U step
  if(iter>1|warm){
    BD=UD(V,Dsq,m)
    xfill <- suvC(U,BD,irow,pcol)
    if (!is.null(debias.matrix)) {
      xres@x=(x@x-xfill)*debias.matrix
    } else {
      xres@x=x@x-xfill
    }
  }else BD=0
  B=t(t(U)%*%xres)+BD
  if(lambda>0)B=UD(B,Dsq/(Dsq+lambda),m)
  Bsvd=svd(B)
  V=Bsvd$u
  Dsq=Bsvd$d
  U=U%*%Bsvd$v

  ## V step
  AD=UD(U,Dsq,n)
  xfill=suvC(AD,V,irow,pcol)
  if (!is.null(debias.matrix)) {
    xres@x=(x@x-xfill)*debias.matrix
  } else {
    xres@x=x@x-xfill
  }
  if(trace.it) obj=(.5*sum(xres@x^2)+lambda*sum(Dsq))/nz
  A=xres%*%V+AD
  if(lambda>0)A=UD(A,Dsq/(Dsq+lambda),n)
  Asvd=svd(A)
  U=Asvd$u
  Dsq=Asvd$d

```

```

V=V %*% Asvd$v
ratio=Frob(U.old,Dsq.old,V.old,U,Dsq,V)

distance <- norm((xfill - x@x)/length(x@x), type="2")
logger[iter] <- distance
if(trace.it) cat(iter, ":",
  "obj", format(round(obj,5)), "ratio", ratio, "distance",
  distance, "\n")
}
if(iter==maxit)warning(paste("Convergence not achieved
  by", maxit, "iterations"))
if(lambda>0&final.svd) {
  AD=UD(U,Dsq,n)
  xfill=suvC(AD,V,irow,pcol)
  xres@x=x@x-xfill
  A=xres%*%V+AD
  Asvd=svd(A)
  U=Asvd$u
  Dsq=Asvd$d
  V=V %*% Asvd$v
  Dsq=pmax(Dsq-lambda,0)

  if(trace.it) {
    AD=UD(U,Dsq,n)
    xfill=suvC(AD,V,irow,pcol)
    xres@x=x@x-xfill
    obj=(.5*sum(xres@x^2)+lambda*sum(Dsq))/nz
    cat("final SVD:", "obj", format(round(obj,5)), "\n")
  }
}
J=min(sum(Dsq>0)+1,J)
out=list(u=U[, seq(J)], d=Dsq[seq(J)], v=V[, seq(J)])
attributes(out)=c(attributes(out), list(lambda=lambda, call=this.call,
  logger=logger), biats)
out
}

```